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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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ADIWIDYA 9 | #SINERGIKANPERAN
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Influence of Landfill Distance to Ground Water Quality in Urban Residential (Case Study: Bakung Landfill, Bandar Lampung)

Tastapyani Kurnia Nufutomo and Rafli Pratama

Environmental Engineering, Infrastructure and Regional Technology Department,
Institut Teknologi Sumatera, South Lampung

tastapyani.kurnia@tl.itera.ac.id

Abstract. Landfill leachate is produced by excess rainwater seeping into the waste layer of the landfill, and eventually enters the ground, then enters the groundwater when it is discharged into shallow water bodies. Leachate absorbs organic and inorganic components through physical, hydrolysis and fermentation processes, therefore it contains high concentrations of organic and inorganic ions, including heavy metals. Bakung Landfill is in Keteguhan Teluk Betung Barat, Lampung. Bakung landfill is located at an altitude of 63 m, and the residential area is at an altitude of 35 m. Bakung landfill waste treatment system still uses an open dumping system, which is the simplest of other waste treatment systems. This study aims for determine the influence of landfill distance to ground water quality in urban residential. The method use based on Indonesian National Standard 06-2412-1991 for purposive sampling, and the parameters are pH, turbidity, BOD, and COD. The obtained groundwater quality analysis results show that parameters such as pH, BOD, COD, exceed the standard quality parameters. The statistical result is lower than 0.05, indicating that the data cannot prove the influence of distance on landfill to ground water quality in urban residential.

1. Introduction

Landfill leachate is produced by excess rainwater seeping into the waste layer of the landfill, and eventually enters the ground, then enters the ground water when it is discharged into shallow water bodies. Leachate absorbs organic and inorganic components through physical, hydrolysis and fermentation processes, therefore it contains high concentrations of organic and inorganic ions, including heavy metals (Fan et al, 2006). The Leachate Contamination Index (LPI) provides a quantitative measure of potential environmental contamination from landfill leachate and information on environmental quality near a specific landfill. If landfill leachate is not safely collected, treated, or discharged, it will cause various pollution problems in soil, surface water, groundwater, and human health. Due to the presence of high concentrations of ammonia, heavy metals, and some organic substances (VOCs), the leachate from landfill will eventually have harmful toxic effects on the ecosystem and humans. Therefore, the leachate is considered to have potential ecotoxic effects because it puts pressure on the components of the ecosystem (Wijekoon et al, 2022).

Bakung Landfill is in Keteguhan Teluk Betung Barat, Lampung. Bakung landfill is located at an altitude of 63 m, and the residential area is at an altitude of 35 m. Bakung landfill waste treatment system still uses an open dumping system, which is the simplest of other waste treatment systems (Geoportall Lampung, 2020). Bandar Lampung City has approximately 1,068,982 residents. The Bakung Landfill has a capacity of 800 tons per day and an area of approximately 14.1 hectares (BPS, 2020). The

Regulation of the Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing No. 03 (2013) on the implementation of infrastructure and waste facilities in the treatment of domestic waste and types of household waste, the final disposal site will be built more than 1 km from the residential (PermenPUPR, 2013), but in fact residential have been established 300 meters around the Bakung Landfill, so there is concern that infiltration water will contaminate residents' ground water quality. Residents around the Bakung landfill complained their ground water was unusable because of its dirty and smelly water. The smell of the water was rusty and brown, and it could not even be washed because the color of the laundry became dark brown stains on clothes (Lampung Post, 2020).

This study aims for determine the influence of landfill distance to ground water quality in urban residential. In addition, this study also analyzed the ground water quality, which is based on the standard quality parameters of PemenKes. No. 32 (2017) on environmental sanitation quality standards and constitution regulation No. 82 (2001) on water quality management and water pollution control.

2. Methods

2.1. Time and Location

This study was carried out for 6 months and the sampling site was located in the Bakung Landfill and at a distance of \pm 3 kilometers, exactly in the Teluk Betung Barat district of the Residential of Keteguhan. In addition, the water quality and leachate were analyzed at the BPLHD laboratory in Lampung province. The sampling location was in Teluk Betung Barat District, Keteguhan Village, Bandar Lampung, Lampung. Except for the sample at 3100 m which is located in Teluk Betung Selatan District, Bandar Lampung. Each location has a ground water well depth of more than 10 m. At a distance of 1400 m the sample point is adjacent to the swamp with the distance between the swamp and the water sample is 46 m.

Figure 1. Bakung Landfill Location (Bappeda Bandar Lampung, 2020)

2.2. Variable

In this study used independent variable and dependent variable. Independent variables are variables that affect the quality of ground water around the Bakung Landfill. The independent variable in this study is the distance between the landfill point and the sampling point. The sampling points are 300 m, 500 m, 700 m, 800 m, 1000 m, 1400 m, 1700 m, 2100 m, 2300 m, 2500 m and 3100 m. The dependent variable is the variable that appears because of the independent variable. The dependent variable in this study is

the parameter quality of the sampling point in the residential area around the Bakung Landfill. The water parameters seen are the turbidity, pH, turbidity, BOD and COD parameters.

2.3. Data collection

The Global Positioning System (GPS) will be used to record samples around the Bakung Landfill location. The sampling method based on National Standard Indonesia (SNI) number 6989-58-2008, that is the procedures and methods for taking water samples. The data will take up to 11 samples, because a simple study can use 10 to 20 samples (Agung, 2006). The sample points taken are at a distance of 300 m, 500 m, 700 m, 800 m, 1000 m, 1400 m, 1700 m, 2100 m, 2300 m, 2500 m, and 3100 m. Time for sampling is in the dry season. Determination of sampling point is in residential the closest to the location of landfill and easy to reach, so every direction is chosen to be around Bakung Landfill. Increasing the distance from the landfill to know reduced the pollution level.

2.4. Data Analysis

The analysis of data is assisted by tables and graphs to facilitate the presentation of the data to the public and cross-sections, including collecting data only at specific times (dry seasons). The collected data will be analysis by linear regression.

3. Results

3.1. Water quality

3.1.1. Turbidity

In the turbidity parameter shown in Figure 2, there is no value that exceeds the quality standard parameter, when compared to PERMENKES No. 32 of 2017 the turbidity quality standard parameter is 25 NTU. However, at 500 m there was an increase in the turbidity value of 7 NTU. Then the turbidity parameter decreased at 700 m – 1000 m, then at 1400 m and 1700 m the turbidity value increased to 3 NTU and 6 NTU. At the next distance the value decreases again. This fluctuations value due to the presence of a new source of pollution, the swamp. Swamps can cause increased turbidity, indicating the presence of bacteria or particles, as well as inorganic and organic matter in the water (Auzar, 2006). This situation is supported by the rain that falls at 1000 m at the time of sampling and the presence of garbage piles in the swamp, so these results will affect the turbidity results.

Figure 2. Turbidity Parameter analysis result

3.1.2. pH

In Figure 3 The pH value of 5 at 300 m has passed the quality standard, and the pH value at 500 m is 6. This shows that the pH value is acidic, but the quality does not exceed the parameter value. Then, at 700 m and 3100 m are showed pH of 7, it means a transition to a neutral pH. This value represents the acid content caused by the contamination of the leachate from landfill.

Figure 3. pH parameter analysis result

3.1.3. BOD

In Figure 4, the values of various locations have passed the parameters of the quality standard, respectively, at distances of 300 m, 500 m, 1000 m, 1400 m, 1700 m, and 2300 m. The BOD quality standard parameter value is 2 mg/l. The highest quality parameter is at 1400 meters with a value of 29 mg/L. This indicates that there are many microorganisms in the water due to the high BOD. The fluctuating value may be due to the existence of new pollution sources, the construction of wells and swamps that affect the quality of groundwater. The TDS, BOD and COD values of the swamp are very high. This is due to the high content of organic matter and microorganisms in the water (Naswir, 2014). During on-site sampling, the amount of garbage and community wastewater was also added to increase the value of the BOD parameter. If the BOD value is high enough and exceeds the quality standard, it can be suspected that there is an indication of water pollution.

Figure 4. BOD parameter analysis result

3.1.4. COD

In figure 5, there are several places that pass the quality standard, which are 300 m, 500 m, 1000 m, 1400 m, and 1700 m. The quality standard of the COD parameter is 10 mg/l. The position with the highest pass quality standard parameter value is at 1400 m, and the test result is 57 mg / L. The groundwater at 1400 m exceeds the standard and cannot be classified as first-class drinking water. Fluctuating data may be due to the construction of swamps and wells. Because the COD value of the swamp is very high, it indicates that the microbes are rich, and also the organic matter (Dade, 2018).

Figure 5. COD Parameter analysis result

3.2. Influence Landfill Distance to Water Quality

In Table 1, all parameters (turbidity, pH, BOD and COD) the Sig value is above 0.05. According to Priyatno (2010), this means that the data obtained cannot prove the influence of the distance in all standard quality parameters on the quality of groundwater around Bakung Landfill, because the Sig value is > 0.05 . The results obtained are consistent with previous studies, which are due to the existence of new and unexpected sources of pollutants in addition to Bakung Landfill (Dwi, 2010). The pollutants such as swamps near the sampling points, change in weather during the sampling period, piles of garbage, and domestic sewage entering the ground water.

Table 1. SPSS Test Result

No.	Parameters	R	R square	A	B	Sig.
1	Turbidity	0.423	0.179	4.541	-0.001	0.195
2	pH	0.568	0.0323	6.131	0	0.068
3	BOD	0.223	0.05	8.758	-0.002	0.509
4	COD	0.199	0.39	17.487	-0.003	0.558

4. Conclusion

The values of pH, BOD, COD exceed the standard water quality parameters. The pH value is 5 at 300 m. The highest value of BOD at 1400 m is 29 mg/l. COD has the highest value at 1400 m, with a value of 57 mg/l. The landfill distance has not influence to ground water quality parameter in urban residential.

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Keluarga Mahasiswa Islam (KAMIL) Pascasarjana ITB,
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